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TLR5 is activated in the blood of humans with high CRP.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We measured total transcription in the blood in humans with low CRP and in humans with high CRP to identify causative factors in cardiovascular disease mediated by inflammation. We describe here activation of TLR5 in humans with high CRP.